

5 things to focus on which can break your cloud computing strategies

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While the world is adopting cloud, many are left with the doubt and threats regarding the consequences applying it. Interconnection of remote servers through which hosted services are delivered online and facilitate storage, management and processing of subscribing organization's data can be daunting. Though this new generation method is spelling significant advantages for businesses, they do confront some challenges in embracing the system such as:

1. Shortfall of resources and proficiency

With the swift advancement of cloud technology, the organizational workload on cloud has increased tremendously. The problem arises during data management which gets compromised to a certain degree due to unavailability of sufficient quantity of strategic tools. Further, there is constant want of competent professionals who are contemporarily skilled to understand the intricacies of the cloud and help organizations' with seamless adoption of and data migration to cloud. The remuneration of cloud experts is exorbitantly high and organizations have to consistently invest in training and skill upgrading of IT staff.

2. Security constraints

Cutting edge cloud technology is giving nightmares to organizations regarding the integrity of their sensitive data. This stems from the fact that the virtual addresses of the servers in which data storing and processing takes place are not revealed to organizations. There is lingering fear that the sanctity of proprietary data would be compromised resulting in costly security breaches. Credentials and authentication mechanisms if hacked by unauthorized personnel can add to the vulnerability of organizations and cause them lose their competitive edge.

3. Cost and performance bottlenecks

Migration to cloud makes the organization susceptible to the idiosyncrasies of service providing agencies' infrastructure. Innovation skyrockets organizational performance but makes it plummet when service provider fails to maintain cloud uptime. These outages can compromise organizational efficiency and productivity by preventing access to strategic data at opportune time. Real time access and prior intimation of downtimes are still problematic.

Cloud computing rationalizes the spending of an organization but the agile character of the services and availability of on-demand 'pay as you use' infrastructural support make it difficult to predict project expenditure beforehand for proper allocation of budget.

4. Strategic cloud control issues

Optimal utilization of cloud based IT resources is contingent on framing of mutually convenient and agreeable procedural policies. The scope need to include controlling and maintenance of cloud infrastructure in alignment with organization mission and vision. However, organizational IT team is not provided complete governance control over the provisions of cloud architecture. Consequently, mitigation of risks in reactive and proactive manner has become difficult.

5. Fragmented usage of cloud and discretionary migration related issues

Majority of companies initially lacked the strategic preparation to adapt to cloud technology. This caused them to resort to ad-hoc techniques to benefit from cloud without having to wait interminably for new infrastructure to be instituted. Further, cloud migration through various service providers at short intervals had to be undertaken due to short-lived data centre contractual obligations and hired tools. In-house teams also explored public cloud's potential to host applications. These improvisations are posing problems in complete integration with standardized cloud framework, sharing of resources in cross-functional mode, bolstering security for robust and centralized governance.

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